

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**Data Study
Group Final
Report:
Global bank**

16-20 April 2018

Machine learning for predicting
and mitigating operational risk

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2557809>

This work was supported by The Alan Turing Institute under the EPSRC grant EP/N510129/1

Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
1.1	Challenge Overview	3
1.2	Data Overview	3
1.3	Main Objectives	4
1.4	Approach	4
1.5	Main Conclusions	5
1.6	Limitations	5
1.7	Recommendations and further work	6
2	Quantitative problem formulation	7
2.1	Time series	7
2.2	Natural Language Processing	8
3	Dataset Overview	8
3.1	Data Description	8
3.2	Data Quality Issues	10
4	Exploratory analysis and visualization of non-text data	11
4.1	iGold dataset	11
4.2	ORX Combined dataset	15
4.3	Identifying Relevant Factors	20
5	Exploratory analysis and visualization of text data	27
5.1	ORX News dataset	28
5.2	iGold dataset	31
6	Time series modeling	33
6.1	Event counts	33
6.2	Alternative and untested approaches	36
7	NLP modeling	36
7.1	Pre-processing unstructured data	36
7.2	Experiment 1: Topic modeling	37
7.3	Experiment 2: Basel Event Classification (Naive Bayes)	39
7.4	Experiment 3: Basel Event Classification (RNN LSTMs)	40
7.5	Experiment 4: Root Cause Classification (RNN LSTMs)	42

8	Future work and research avenues	45
9	Team Members	47
	References	49

1 Executive Summary

1.1 Challenge Overview

In the wake of the global financial crisis in 2007-2008, the Basel II and III global regulatory accords, amongst others, stipulate the holding of so-called regulatory capital to off-set potential losses.

The risk of potential loss needs to be estimated by statistical models. A type of risk newly emphasized in Basel II and III is operational risk - concerning losses caused by fraud, bad practices, disasters, or process failures, or, more generally, human and environment/infrastructure factors.

The challenge is to develop accurate models for predicting operational risk, with the goal of preventing avoidable risks and mitigating unavoidable ones through sufficient regulatory capital.

1.2 Data Overview

Multiple datasets related to operational risk were provided:

1. Tabular records of major and minor operational loss events of 95 major banks from approximately the last 15 years. This dataset is referred to as the ORX Combined dataset.
2. Tabular records of all operational risk events at the challenge owner bank from approximately the last 15 years. This dataset is referred to as the iGold dataset.
3. News reports on major operational loss events linked from 1. This dataset is referred to as the ORX News dataset.
4. Further unstructured data attached to 2, such as event reports, definitions, etc.

We will refer to the tabular records as "structured", and to the other datasets as "unstructured".

1.3 Main Objectives

The main challenge questions were to:

1. Identify robust, accurate, and optimally interpretable models to predict risk, by type of risk - i.e. the Basel Event Type (e.g. internal fraud, system failures, etc.) and also the severity of the risk - i.e. the size of the loss
2. Leverage insights from these models to infer and identify candidate drivers, as well as potential early warning signs.
3. Develop appropriate natural language processing (NLP) tools to systematize information in the unstructured datasets.

1.4 Approach

Proof-of-concept work during the week focused on forecasting event risk from the structured data, and building NLP models to extract information from the unstructured data. The eventual outlook is to combine the two, but this was not done during the (short) week.

For risk forecasting, the following methods were applied:

1. Exploratory time series analyses using seasonal decomposition;
2. Analysis of the annual distribution of the number of losses; and
3. Autoregressive time series models of count data.

As NLP methods, the following methods were applied:

1. Topic modeling using Gensim and Latent Dirichlet Analysis (LDA);
2. LSTM classification of Basel events with pre-trained twitter word embeddings and news trained SVD word vectors;
3. LSTM classification of root causes in ORX data using pre-trained twitter word embeddings; and
4. Naive Bayes classification as a baseline of Basel events trained on 'Event description' text, achieving an accuracy of 84%.

1.5 Main Conclusions

The study provides preliminary proof-of-concept for the potential usefulness of statistical and NLP approaches in operational risk modelling:

Time series analyses on the structured datasets suggested that over monthly time scale, loss risk distributions were reasonably stable (Section 4.3); trends occurred over the time scale of years, and autocorrelation, where detected, was over the short-term and mainly restricted to Basel type 7 events. A probabilistic event risk model was accurate in modelling the event distribution by risk type (Section 6.1).

NLP analyses show that there are qualitative differences in frequent words between different Basel event types or root cause categories in the iGold dataset and the ORX News dataset (Section 5). In the iGold dataset, seasonality among the most common words used for description of the events appears to be absent. The NLP predictive models are able to identify event type in the iGold data, and root causes ("Digest Text" field) in the ORX News dataset.

1.6 Limitations

1. Our conclusions were limited by certain aspects of the data. The iGold dataset appeared to be well-curated. The larger ORX data contained a number of reporting and data acquisition biases (Section 3.2), requiring domain-specific knowledge of practices in collecting and reporting on losses to correctly interpret the findings.
2. Due to time constraints only a limited number of prediction architectures could be tested - none included modelling the magnitudes of losses, or risk modelling with NLP features. Systematic investigation of the latter would be required to make the statement that the unstructured data is useful at all for regulatory capital estimations.
3. As with all time series and time sequential models, past performance (of models) is not indicative of future performance. Regime shifts

in the future may have an unforeseen impact on the dynamics of operational losses.

1.7 Recommendations and further work

The week has provided proof-of-concept for usefulness of statistical and NLP techniques for operational risk modelling. However, construction of a full risk model is still in early exploratory phases and will require more time as well as systematic investigation of modelling techniques with respect to their performance and informativity. As part of this, one should investigate:

1. Using additional variables in the ORX dataset for risk forecasting
2. Further classical statistical (GLM, ARIMA, GARCH), and black-box forecasting approaches (machine learning style: GP, ensembles, deep learning)
3. Composite models with NLP feature extraction feeding into the risk models - are the unstructured data useful?

Further in the future are use of the above and refinement of such models for automated event detection, anomaly detection, and informing mitigation and prevention measures.

Interesting avenues to pursue in the context of NLP:

1. Explore further modelling architectures for automated labelling (Basel type, root cause) of reports, especially deep learning based ones.
2. Connect the above with event modeling such as event risk and loss severity.

Limitations of the data may be addressed by augmentation and improvement of the acquisition process:

1. Develop a richer corpus for Basel event types by scraping external data, leveraging internal documentation etc.

2. Compare external reporting on Basel risk events vs internal information in terms of accuracy, sentiment, etc.
3. Populate and validate the Root Cause field for internal risk events.

2 Quantitative problem formulation

This section provides a brief explanation of the scientific modelling approaches adopted and their relation to the domain questions.

2.1 Time series

The first main challenge question is to identify robust, accurate, and optimally interpretable models to predict risk, by type of risk - i.e. the Basel event type (corresponding to internal fraud, system failures, etc.) and also the severity of the risk.

As this "prediction" lies in the temporal future, this falls into the domain of forecasting. Since the quantity of interest is risk of event occurrence and the event's severity, the prediction is of a continuous (event occurrence), labelled (severity) outcome. As a stylized fact in the area, the exact time point of an occurrence cannot be predicted in the stylized case, while a general expectation of how many events occur may be predictable.

There are two types of forecasting models which are capable of this: count forecasts, and fully probabilistic forecasts of the risk and/or the risk/severity distribution.

Forecasting models as described above may then further be used as a basis, in a second step, for more complex tasks such as event detection or risk capital calculations.

2.2 Natural Language Processing

Modelling of text itself (as opposed to its retrieval) falls in the domain of natural language processing (NLP).

While eventually, one would wish the models to inform risk calculations, a simple task to begin with (and usually the first step) in the given scenario is attempting to learn the high-level content of the documents provided.

The most pertinent content descriptors, for the loss reports, are Basel event type and root cause - thus the most pertinent NLP models of the above type are (so-called) classification strategies which assign, to a document about the loss report, Basel event type or root cause. The labels provided with the data allow for training of the models, and for evaluation of the classification strategies' performance.

A further, basic NLP task for modelling the text is topic modelling, that is, automated assignment of topics to the text, as well as word vector extraction via Word2Vec strategies which numerically encode "meaning" found in the text. These can be used to extract keywords, key phrases and sentences from text descriptions and automate Basel event type labeling process. In contrast to the classification methods, topic modelling and Word2Vec attempts to find quantitative descriptors which are not already present in expert labels (such as Basel type), and constitute a (so-called) unsupervised approach. While these methods may find new information, the value of the extracted quantifiers is impossible to check without an ulterior task for their use where ground truth to compare against is present (such as risk prediction, or the text classification task).

3 Dataset Overview

3.1 Data Description

Datasets with information on individual Operational Risk Events:

1. Name: ORX Combined
 Description: Tabular records of major and minor operational loss events from 95 major banks from approximately the last 15 years. No free text field descriptions.
 NAME IN R-DRIVE: EL Combined (timestamp 18/04/2018 11:51)
2. Name: iGold
 Description: Tabular records of all operational risk events at the challenge owner bank from approximately the last 15 years. Includes free text description of event created and validated by the challenge owner bank.
 NAME IN R-DRIVE: iGold extract_SEARCH_LOSS_RESULTS_10 Oct 17_Sep17ME_vf_filtered (timestamp 16/04/2018 18:04)
3. Name: ORX News
 Description: News reports on major operational loss events linked from 1. Includes free text description of event created by ORX employees which is a summary of the published news report.
 NAME IN R DRIVE: ORX News 18th December 2017 (timestamp 03/04/2018 11:48)

Datasets with definitions of fields and terms used in the datasets above:

1. Name: OpRiskRegisters 2016_List_Filtered
 Description: Challenge Owner Bank Definitions of the ORR Level 1 Types - links to iGold dataset using Orr Id (= Orr Level1 Type Code in iGold) and Risk Title (= Orr Level1 Type Name in iGold)
2. Name: bis.org/bcbs/qisoprisknote.pdf
 Description: Regulator provided definitions of Basel Event Types in Annex 1 - links to iGold dataset Event Type Category (Level 1) (= Event Type L1 in iGold) and Categories (Level 2) (= Event Type L2 in iGold)

There are descriptive statistics about the datasets on the git-lab [repository](http://10.220.0.151/global_bank/bankrepo/blob/master/notebooks/00\%20Description\%20of\%20the\%20Datasets.ipynb)

3.2 Data Quality Issues

3.2.1 ORX News Dataset

Several Data Quality Issues were highlighted by the Global Bank SMEs. The root cause in the ORX data is not always correct for the Public Domain Data (ORX News) as ORX have just used what was reported in the media to try and determine the root cause, rather than internal bank data. In addition, the primary root cause of the event is missing in 10% of the ORX News data. For the anonymized Data (ORX Combined), the Root Cause is optional for the bank submitting the data, and if the field is not populated then a best guess is made by ORX and therefore can not be relied on as ground truth. The Basel event type field may also be inaccurate in the ORX data.

3.2.2 iGold Dataset

In the iGold Dataset the Root cause field was sparsely populated as it is not a mandatory field. The Basel event type should be correct, as it has been validated internally in the global bank.

For the internal data, reporting practices changed over the period of observation. Of particular note, the requirement to report smaller losses came into effect around 2002. For the time series analysis, we considered two filtered datasets; one in which all losses less than USD200,000 were removed and another in which only events that were logged after 2012-01-01 were included.

In total, there are three main datasets that we work on: iGold, ORX News and ORX Combined. The data quality issues are mainly around the first two datasets, such as missing information and inaccurate entries in the root cause domain in ORX News.

4 Exploratory analysis and visualization of non-text data

Exploratory analysis of the datasets was conducted in order to inform further experiments. Visualization and descriptive statistics are shown in the following.

4.1 iGold dataset

We conduct some preliminary analyses for the iGold dataset. This dataset contains 4489 observations and 41 columns. Generally, the volatility is a very important factor in financial time series. However, the overall view of the Gross Loss Amount is relatively stationary which means most losses are under certain amount, except some huge losses happening occasionally. We verify our expectation by performing Portmanteau Test which computes Ljung-Box statistics. The corresponding p-value is 1 which indicates a very weak autocorrelation function for all lags. More tests could be applied to split data according to different type of losses.

The following figure shows the distribution of daily events for the entire dataset. The first event occurred in 1994 and the most recent event occurred in 2016.

Figure 1: Distribution of daily events for the entire dataset

Figure 2 shows the distribution of training samples amongst Basel categories for the iGold dataset. It is clear that the vast majority of training data points fall in the EL7 category and this will have ramifications when classifiers are trained on the dataset.

Figure 2: Distribution of EL-types for the 4,489 data points (after removing for Total Gross Losses of \$0.00)

Figure 3: Log transformed total gross loss (in USD) versus EL type for each month of the year. Dots represent the median values for that month.

Figure 4: Log transformed total gross loss (in USD) versus EL type for each day of the week. Dots represent the median values for that day.

4.2 ORX Combined dataset

The ORX Combined dataset contains over 500,000 observations and 18 columns which contain information regarding the loss including different levels of values and potential factors. We focus on the Gross Loss Amount and Loss Date of Occurrence.

1. We first order the data of Gross Loss Amount by days, months and years. Importantly, whether the loss is related to the credit is also taken into account.
2. We compare the number of losses in each level of values in terms of days, months and years categorized.
3. The amount of losses has also been considered in terms of days, months and years.

4. Preliminary tests are performed to find the autocorrelation effects of the loss time series.

Our findings are as follows:

1. The violin plots of the loss have a similar shape categorized by the credit regardless of days and months. This means the number of each level amount of loss follows a similar pattern.

Figure 5: The violin plot of the number of loss events happening for each day related to the credit. The difference between right and left side is not obvious.

Figure 6: The violin plot of the number of loss events happening for each month related to the credit. Again the credit factor may not be important in this case

This is unexpected because we initially believed that credit should be a very important factor when predicting the amount of loss. Here a violin plot is similar to a box plot and it could not only reflect the quantities of the loss such as median value, but also show the probability density of the data at different values of the loss.

2. The average number of losses every day tended to increase since 2000 and remain stable after 2004. On other side, the average number of losses every week kept increasing from 1994 until 2013 and started to decrease afterwards (certain actions may be taken to prevent the loss). In both cases, there are certain huge number of losses occasionally.

Figure 7: The number of loss incidents happening every day from 1900 to 2016

Figure 8: The number of loss incidents happening every week from 1900 to 2016

3. Autocorrelation effects are present in the time series of the loss. However, each coefficient of the model is very small and therefore further investigation is required. [2].

Among the ORX Combined dataset we receive additional information about the region where events occur.

Events by Region from 2010 through 2015

Figure 9: Distribution of events occurring by region between 2010 and 2015

Figure 10: The rolling volatility as the standard deviation of total loss (in USD) of all events occurring during the prior 30-day moving window from 2000 through 2015 in the ORX combined dataset

One hypothesis would be that the length of time in delay between event occurrence and the reporting of this event is correlated with the severity of the loss (in total gross USD). A Pearson correlation of 0.25 confirms a weak relationship between the log-loss and even weaker 0.094 for untransformed loss.

Figure 11: log transformed total gross loss (in USD) versus delay (difference in reporting of the event and the actual event). Pearson correlation of 0.25 in the plot.

4.3 Identifying Relevant Factors

Each potential factor was studied by performing a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test on the categories of a factor and the total gross loss (in USD) of each event. Significance ($p < 0.05$) implies that one or more of the categories of this factor is important in determining the total gross loss and relevant

for further study. The test assumes non-normality and we confirmed each distribution before running with Shapiro-Wilk ($p < 10^{-10}$).

Among two major categories (EL type and region) in the combined dataset, both are considered statistically significant using the Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test ($p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$) in both the original and the subset from 2010 through 2015 towards the total gross loss of events.

4.3.1 Identifying Risk Events within Relevant Factors

For statistically significant factors that influence the total gross loss, a Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test was performed using pair-wise comparisons of each in-group vs the rest of the events after confirming non-normality (Shapiro-Wilks test). The final set of p-values was adjusted using the Benjamini and Hochberg multiple-hypothesis testing correction before determining which categories of a given factor were significant.

All Basel types of an event are associated with significant total gross loss with the exception of external fraud (Type 2, $p = 0.67$) and damage to physical assets (Type 5, $p = 0.12$) within the internal iGold dataset. Within the ORX Combined dataset all the Basel types became relevant risk factors associated with loss events.

Out of all the currencies which had reported loss events for the internal iGold dataset, only the Brazilian Real (BRL, $p = 1.24 \times 10^{-5}$), British Pound (GBP, 5.73×10^{-2}), and U.S. Dollar (USD, $p = 2.37 \times 10^{-2}$), and U.S. Dollar (USD, $p = 2.37 \times 10^{-2}$) were significant when standardized in common currency. This implies they are the currencies associated with riskier events.

Figure 12: For each reported currency of loss the total gross loss in USD was plotted. USD had the greatest number of events with outlier losses.

All geographic regions within the ORX Combined dataset are associated with riskier transactions in total gross loss with the exception of Africa ($p = 0.12$).

4.3.2 Univariate distribution modeling

From previous data investigation we know the data is non-normal (Shapiro-Wilks, $p < 1 \times 10^{-30}$). Further understanding of the exact nature of the underlying distribution will be helpful to selecting further tools of analysis. The rate of event occurrences was aggregated over weekly time frames to avoid weekend effects (i.e., less activity over weekends).

Using a maximum-likelihood fitting strategy the negative binomial distribution was the most similar to the data. Using the null model that the distribution of events is normal, the best fit had a Bayesian information criterion difference that was very strong ($\Delta BIC = [14, 45]$) as each year was processed separately and the parameter estimates for each year was overlaid in red (above) for Basel type 7. Each Basel type was processed separately.

Figure 13: Distribution of events by year from 2001 to 2015 with a negative binomial distribution fit overlay for Basel type 7

To quantify the fitness of the model, QQ-plots were used for the data itself for a year versus the derived data with expected values given the fitted negative binomial model. A linear model is fit and the residuals capture the degree of deviation from the negative binomial model.

Figure 14: QQ-plots of annual events from 2001 to 2015 compared to expected values from the fitted negative binomial distribution

From the QQ-plot of the negative binomial models, 2001 most accurately fit this distribution type with an R^2 of 0.82 versus the pure model. It's worth pointing out that the negative binomial models are not compared against other distribution types.

The developed world category include those events occurring in North America or Western Europe. The developing world categorization includes those events occurring in Africa, Asia Pacific, Latin America & Caribbean, and Eastern Europe.

Figure 15: QQ-plots of annual events from 2001 to 2015 compared to expected values from the fitted negative binomial distribution for the developed world (Western Europe and North America)

Figure 16: QQ-plots of annual events from 2001 to 2015 compared to expected values from the fitted negative binomial distribution from the developing world (Africa, Asia Pacific, Latin America & Caribbean, and Eastern Europe)

Despite varying among different years, both the developed and developing world seem to have converged to similar levels around 0.45 and 0.42 of R^2 for an ideal negative binomial distribution.

4.3.3 Attempts at seasonal decomposition using STL

Looking at the time series of total losses over time, an attempt was made to uncover any seasonality using seasonal decomposition based on LOESS, also known as STL [3]. STL has several advantages over classical decomposition and X-12-ARIMA since it can handle any type of seasonality. The seasonal component can change over time, the trend smoothing parameter can be controlled by the user and it can be robust to outliers, but these however will show in the remainder term.

Although some seasonality was extracted with the algorithm on the yearly pattern, it is heavily conditioned on the outliers in the year 2008, affecting even the robust version. These seasonality patterns on the other hand, could potentially be influenced by the reporting process, with tendencies to place an event without a clear origin date in some specific position in the year. With the current dataset this method proved not effective for trend and seasonality estimation.

Potentially could be used as the trend and seasonal components are better towards the end of the series, but it would require data segmentation and careful dataset adaptation using expert knowledge.

Figure 17: Output from a STL robust run with data thresholded at 2008 and seasonal window = 367. Initially it can be seen the trend disturbances generated by extreme values in 2008, these disappear over time, settling in a flat trend towards the end of the time series.

5 Exploratory analysis and visualization of text data

Before moving to more advanced NLP approaches we first explored the text descriptions in both the iGold dataset and the ORX News dataset using some visualizations of the most common words stratifying by either

the Basel types or root cause categories. For both datasets we used term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf). This is a statistic that identifies words that are most important to a document or set of documents and thus controls for the frequency of words across the whole corpus. For the purposes of this task we could group text descriptions into either their Basel or risk types to identify important words that delineate the groupings.

Following standard text processing such as removing stop words and tokenizing we also removed numbers and any series of 2 or more capital letters which occurred in a row. From discussions with subject matter experts these words were acronyms of businesses or currencies and were deemed irrelevant.

5.1 ORX News dataset

We first grouped data points into their Basel event type. This showed clear differences in popular words between the different types, see Figure 18. For example for Basel type EL02 (External Fraud), the 3 most important distinguishing words were “malware”, “hackers” and “cyberattack” and for EL01 (Internal Fraud) the 3 most important were “embezzled”, “defrauded” and “fraudulent”.

Figure 18: 20 most important words ranked by tf-idf scores grouped into Basel event types

The ORX News data also groups news articles into root cause categories so we performed the same analysis grouping by this variable. Curiously many of the words in the "External Causes" category were medically related.

Figure 19: 20 most important words ranked by TF-IDF scores grouped into root cause categories

It is worth noting that the root cause field ("Cause 1 Level 1 Name") is used as the target for prediction. The distribution below shows under 100 examples of the classes "Internal Systems Failures" and "Governance & Structure". This will effect the performance of the models, as will also be discussed later.

Figure 20: Distribution of root causes in ORX News

5.2 iGold dataset

We performed the same analysis for the internal iGold dataset. This again showed that types were identifiable based on words with high tf-idf. For example "fraud" and "misappropriation" were the words with the highest score for the internal fraud category and "executed" and "booking" were associated with category 7 which involves process.

Figure 21: 20 most important words ranked by TF-IDF scores grouped into Basel event type categories for the iGold dataset

This analysis showed that it is possible to extract signal from the textual descriptions of the articles and events that appear meaningful and relate to the Basel event types and root cause designations. This approach could be easily adapted to identify words that are important for large losses or to explore if important words change over time to identify temporal trends. Another avenue would be to investigate if a tf-idf based model could be used to identify the Basel types.

It is worth mentioning that the variables used for NLP were 'Event Type L1' as target variable and the text in the 'Event Description' or 'Event Summary Description' as input variables for the models. The prevalence of 'EL7' type, which accounts for 75% of the data, will inevitably affect the performance of the models.

Figure 22: Distribution of the seven Event types (Event Type L1) IN iGold

6 Time series modeling

6.1 Event counts

We investigated the temporal dynamics of the number of losses over time, focusing on models that could potentially provide short to medium term forecasts of number of losses. Detailed analysis focused on losses reported after 2012-01-01, as reporting practices were relatively uniform over this time period and so are unlikely to confound the analysis of events. Counts of losses by week and by type (EL1-EL7) were generated from the data and analyzed using integer-valued time series approaches.

Borrowing from the literature on modeling of infectious diseases [Meyer, Held and Hohle 2017] (<http://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v077.i11>), we initially applied endemic-epidemic models of the event counts using the ‘hhh4’ model as implemented in the R package ‘surveillance’. This model assumes that, conditional on past observations, counts Y_{it} from units $i = 1, \dots, I$ over some discrete time period $t = 1, \dots, T$ can be modeled as a negative binomial distribution with mean μ_{it} and overdispersion parameters $\psi_i > 0$ such that the conditional variance of Y_{it} is

$$\mu_{it}(1 + \psi_i \mu_{it}).$$

$$\mu_{it} = e_{it}\nu_{it} + \lambda_{it}Y_{i,t-1} + \phi_{it} \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ji}Y_{j,t-1}$$

This model can be considered as an extension of a negative binomial generalized linear model that can accommodate dependence over time through autoregressing current observations on past observations. The model can also include seasonal components and cross-correlations between different units.

We fitted separate ‘hhh4’ models to count data from EL4, EL6, and EL7 in the iGold dataset, initially assuming a lag of 1 week in the autoregressive component and an annual seasonal component. The model fits from EL4 were consistent with a seasonally varying Poisson process, in which losses were slightly more frequent towards the end of the year, with no evident upward or downward trend, no evidence of overdispersion. This seasonal trend was replicated in EL6 and EL7, although these events showed more overdispersion with as significant autoregressive component.

The overdispersion in the ‘hhh4’ model may be driven in part by misspecification of the endemic component as a sinusoidal trend. To investigate the robustness of the results, we fitted a negative binomial autoregressive model to all event types, assuming a separate intercept term for each event type and a common ‘endemic’ component modeled using a cubic spline, again assuming an autoregressive lag of 1 week using the R package ‘gamlss’. This model revealed longer-term fluctuations in the rate of losses per week than the annual sinusoidal model, although this phenomenon was driven by the more common event types. Due to time limitations, a full multivariable analysis of differences between event types was not possible, but separate regression fits to the most frequent event types (3, 4, 6, and 7) suggested differences in the overall trend, the level of overdispersion, and the level of autocorrelation. The goodness of fit for these models on the iGold dataset based on probability plot correlation coefficient (PPCC) plots was extremely good; however, the goodness of fit for the ORX combined data was much poorer, presumably due to the greater heterogeneity in the data (not shown).

Event type	Lag (se)	Smoothing (se)	Sigma (se)	Δ BIC for overdispersion
3	-0.23 (0.16)	-0.39 (0.08)	-2.31 (2.19)	5.5
4	-0.05 (0.13)	-0.14 (0.07)	-1.73 (1.12)	4.8
6	0.02 (0.04)	-0.08 (0.04)	-2.98 (1.53)	5.2
7	0.02 (0.01)	0.03 (0.02)	-3.51 (0.58)	1.0

Table 1: Parameter estimates for the gamlss fits to each event type (log link). Hypothesis testing for overdispersion was performed by comparing the Bayesian Information Criterion of a model assuming a negative binomial family with one assuming a Poisson distribution

Figure 23: Dynamics of weekly event counts for the iGold dataset, 2012-present for event types 3, 4, 6, and 7. Colors represent zero/non-zero counts, and black lines represent fitted values from applying a gamlss model to each dataset.

6.2 Alternative and untested approaches

In these analyses, the timing of the loss, the magnitude of the loss, and the delay in recognizing the loss were analyzed independently. Ideally, these should be modeled jointly with a view to identifying potential causal associations. We explored marked point processes using the ‘PtProcess’ library in R, but found little signal of autocorrelation in the dataset or an association between the magnitude of the loss and the rate of subsequent losses.

At least for the internal data, on the timescale of at least months, the distribution of losses per week, the magnitude of the loss and the delay between the loss occurring were reasonably stationary. This suggests that a generative model of losses can be built relatively easily; a prototype model that generates losses based on samples from the joint distribution of loss types, delays, and magnitudes was developed using the ‘simmer’ package in R, which has the potential to be able to be used for detecting anomalies in future losses that may indicate a shift in the dynamics.

The methods used are based on classical frequentist statistics; computational approaches to fitted models under the Bayesian paradigm are arguably more flexible; the model used to analyze event counts can be implemented easily within the Bayesian software package ‘stan’. However, such approaches require sensible choices for priors. For example, the analysis of extreme events can be facilitated by expert opinion on the fraction of losses over a threshold amount.

7 NLP modeling

7.1 Pre-processing unstructured data

For all the analyses that follow, we implemented the following processing steps so that the NLP algorithms could be applied in a consistent manner. We removed capitals, stop words and non alpha-numeric characters before tokenizing the words.

Some of the approaches required word embeddings to produce vector representations of words. We used a pre-trained word vector representation dataset that used the GloVe algorithm and twitter data to train. We also generated our own word vector representations using the ORX News dataset and a matrix factorization method which does not require neural networks for training. This was promising and showed similar performance to the GloVe twitter set and would likely to result in increased performance with more data due to the specific nature of the training corpus. For example with this word embedding, the most similar words to "credit" were "suise" and "agricole", such associations would only likely to be observed by training the data using a domain specific corpus. For the remainder of the NLP section when required we used the GloVe twitter set.

7.2 Experiment 1: Topic modeling

We use Gensim and LDA to model the topic representations of all the 'Event description' texts in the iGold dataset and visualize the results by pyLDAvis [4, 5]. This is an unsupervised learning problem.

Topic modeling is a form of dimensionality reduction where a text is represented in its topic space rather than its feature space. Specifically, words are grouped together by topics and a text is a mixture of words - i.e. sub-topics, each having a certain weight. The topic of a text is calculated based on its sub-topics and their weights.

7.2.1 Task descriptions

The task is to model distribution of topics of the 'Event description' texts and then link this to the seven Basel level 1 event types (possibly also the level 2 event types) already defined in the iGold dataset. Based on this, the model can automatically label the event type of an unseen text by finding the most similar text in the iGold dataset and assigning the same event type.

7.2.2 Experimental set-up

The following steps have been taken in this experiment:

1. Modeling the topics of the 'Event description' texts (the number of topics can be set manually) and returning the keywords of each topic ranked by the weight of each word
2. Transforming new texts to their topic distribution
3. Feeding in a new text (such as one from the ORX News dataset) and finding the most similar text in the iGold dataset with an assigned event type.
4. Visualizing LDA results by pyLDAvis. It shows the distribution of topics and the list of keywords for each topic in a interactive fashion

For demonstration purpose, an example visualization on a sample dataset is given below.

Figure 24: An example visualization using pyLDAvis on a sample dataset

7.2.3 Results and testing

This accuracy of the model, i.e. the accuracy of event type predicted is checked against the definitions of Basel Event Types in Annex 1 (bis.org/bcbs/qisoprisknote.pdf). For instance, if the definition of event type 4 is fed in, the (most) similar text(s) returned should also be of type 4. However, the current model doesn't have a consistent performance. Moreover, as mentioned earlier, event type 7 accounts for nearly 75% of the data, the results returned are biased to Event type 7.

7.2.4 Further work

This experiment can be applied to the ORX News dataset. A recommendation system could be built to automatically label new texts by similarity comparison. More suitable pre-processing and robust tests should be applied to the model. By using a more balanced dataset and a more refined keyword lists or corpus could potentially improve the model.

7.3 Experiment 2: Basel Event Classification (Naive Bayes)

7.3.1 Task Descriptions

The approach is to build a Baseline with a simple model such as Naive Bayes Classifier to identify the seven types of events in the iGold dataset.

7.3.2 Experimental Set-Up

This simple model achieves 77% of accuracy using the 'Event Summary Description' for training, which has less words but important ones to describe the type of event. Evaluating on the 'Event Description' text, the model achieves 84% of accuracy.

The idea is to build multi-class classifiers and binary classifiers for the important event types such as 'EL4' that represent higher losses than the rest. 'EL4' is 10% of the rows in the iGold dataset.

7.3.3 Further work

Several classifiers can be tested and depending on the results this type of model can be deployed using 'Scikit-learn' ensemble models.

A couple of experiments can be tested in the future.

1. Creating a target variable with the 'EL4' that is around 7.5% in the iGold dataset. This would help to predict types with high loss.
2. Creating a target variable calculated with the first decile of the loss variable in USD. This would classify a high loss event from the description of the event.

7.4 Experiment 3: Basel Event Classification (RNN LSTMs)

7.4.1 Task Descriptions

This experiment aimed to classify the text descriptions of the events by Basel event type (Event Type L1) in the iGold dataset. This could decrease the amount of time required by analysts to populate databases of loss events by automatically populating fields in the database. However, a more ambitious outcome would be the natural language processing of text data throughout the bank, which could be used to inform time series models of the losses.

7.4.2 Experimental Set-Up

We are mapping the textual description of an event to one of the seven risk event types. Each word (or first n words) is transformed into vector

representation via a look-up table of pre-trained embeddings [https://nlp.stanford.edu/data/GloVe/twitter.27B.zip]. These vectors are used as input into a neural network model composed of one LSTM layer with 100 units and one dense fully connected layer with softmax activation and seven outputs. The categorical cross-entropy is used as loss function and the optimizer is Adam. We used the Keras package with TensorFlow backend to build our model.

*Figure: Distribution of the 7 event classes and their split into trainset and test set

Figure 25: Distribution of the seven event types and their split into train set and test set

7.4.3 Results

Due to lack of time, a proper hyper-parameter search was not performed. In our set-up we used first 40 words of each report and 10 epochs. 4000 events were used for training and 489 for testing. 20% of the training set was used for validation. The final accuracy of predicting the correct event label on the test set is 84.6%. The confusion matrix in the log scale (due to uneven class distribution) is shown in the figure below.

Figure 26: Confusion matrix in log scale (there were no events from class 5 (position 4 on the plot) in the test set)

	Recall	Precision
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.75	0.43
4	0.57	0.38
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00
7	0.95	0.92

Table 2: Recall and precision of individual classes

7.5 Experiment 4: Root Cause Classification (RNN LSTMs)

7.5.1 Task Descriptions

Hypothesis - Root causes ("Cause 1 Level 1 Name" field) of Basel events can be predicted using textual descriptions ("Digest Text" field) which is

sourced from news agencies in the ORX News dataset.

There are two broad parts to this task. 1. Identify the sentences in the text that relate to causality. 2. Use features from sections of text to predict root causes.

Due to time restrictions we only had the opportunity to address the second of these. It should be noted that information extraction pattern induction techniques to identify causal trigger words is one approach that may be successful for the first part.

7.5.2 Experimental Set-Up

We apply the text pre-processing described above to reduce the sparsity of the features and remove known uninformative words. Namely, Removal of stop words, non-alpha-numeric characters, lowercasing, and splitting out the "UPDATE" section of the text. Finally we converted the tokens into numeric vectors for training our model by using GloVe mappings. These word embeddings are pre-trained on 1 billion twitter tokens. This is not ideal given the task is in the operational risk domain, however these are rich embeddings due to the large volume of text used to train them. We use the first 40 characters of the pre-processed digest text.

We chose a neural network approach for this multi-class classification task. The feature vectors in the training set are the input to 2 layer LSTM. The output layer is vector of length 5, corresponding to the number of classes. We ran the experiment with 10 epochs using the 'Adam' optimizer.

We randomly held out 15% of the 5800 data examples for testing using stratification. The distribution across classes for the test and train set is shown in the figure below.

Figure 27: Distribution of classes of train, test and overall dataset

7.5.3 Results

We achieved an accuracy of 0.87 across classes.

	Processes_pred	People_pred	External_pred	Tech Systems	Governance_pred
Processes_gold	273	30	12	3	0
People_gold	86	166	45	0	0
External_gold	14	29	173	9	0
Tech-Systems_gold	5	0	4	10	0
Governance_gold	8	5	1	0	0

Table 3: Confusion matrix of results, where _pred refers to the prediction, and _gold refers to the labels provided in the ORX News dataset

The diagonal shows the the true positive classifications. All 14 examples of 'Governance and Structure' root causes were not successfully classified and instead fell to the 3 majority classes. This logically requires error analysis to determine whether the incorrect classifications are ambiguous.

	Recall	Precision
Processes	0.86	0.71
People / Staff	0.56	0.72
External	0.77	0.74
Internal Systems Failures	0.53	0.45
Governance & Structure	0.00	n/a

Table 4: Recall and precision of individual classes

We see that Precision in the three well represented classes is stable around 0.7 but that falls significantly with the smaller classes. It is worth noting that although there are 109 and 88 examples in the smaller classes, "Internal Systems failures" still achieves 0.53 recall and 0.45 precision which shows that this model has a good discriminatory power for this class.

7.5.4 Conclusions

These experiments demonstrate that prediction of root causes using news reports of Basel events is possible with good accuracy. This can serve as a Baseline for further improvements.

The next step is to perform an error analysis of the false positives to see whether there is real confusability in the label types. In addition the imbalance in the training and test set and the poor performance of the "Internal Systems Failures" and "Governance and Structures" suggests that these classes should be oversampled.

8 Future work and research avenues

The univariate analysis of the event time series should naturally be extended to one that captures extreme counts. A natural distribution would be the Hermite distribution since this would capture the superposition of independent processes with a large hierarchy of rates [6]. Looking at the plots of the negative binomial fit by eye one sees that

there is a large tail that spoils the fit. A Hermite distribution with large separation of rates has similar behavior. This is in keeping with the underlying suspicion that the Basel event types at level 1 are too broad a category and thus capture vastly differing underlying processes.

One further avenue to test this conjecture is to see if Basel types at level 2 fit the univariate model better; here, penalized regression approaches are likely to be necessary in order to accommodate the large number of factors at level 2. Furthermore, joint multivariate time series modeling of the different event types may help to understand how the different types of loss may be coupled.

The study of the rates for different Basel types (when combined with the known mean of the net loss for each Basel type) allows one to predict expected loss for each event type. The utility of this is that one can then attempt to model changes in the expected cost for changes in rate brought on by external factors such as regulatory changes.

So far, we have not used the tools we have developed to predict the count rate or severity of loss events. The relative stability of the counts and magnitudes of losses over the temporal horizon of interest (three months to a year) suggests that forecasting the overall distribution of detected events in the medium term should be straightforward, if coupled with methods to detect anomalies from this distribution.

Of further interest is the use of the information on the delay between the occurrence and the detection of the loss in order to perform 'nowcasting' - identifying how many losses at the present have occurred but have yet to be detected. When coupled with methods for extreme values, both in terms of the number and magnitude of losses, the models developed here could form a central part in projecting the dynamics of losses.

These approaches would be most powerful if developed alongside generative models (e.g. discrete event simulations, agent based models) that accommodate factors such as working days, effort in identifying losses, etc. A qualitative understanding of how losses occur, how they are detected and how they are reported would be necessary in order to build a generative model that is realistic enough for detailed scenario analysis.

Our results show that NLP techniques allow information on operational

risk events to be extracted from text data. Recent media reports indicate that it is indeed possible to forecast such events, but that vast quantities of data on employee behavior and market conditions are required. We therefore recommend reproducing the study with a wider selection of data, e.g. employee emails. Specific recommendations for enhancing our analyses are as follows.

1. Develop a richer corpora for Basel Event Types (scraping external data, leveraging internal documentation)
2. Compare external reporting on Basel Risk Events vs Internal information on them - accuracy, sentiment, etc
3. Root Cause Field - populate and validate for (subset) of internal risk events.
4. Machine Learning algorithms - it would be worth re-weighting the training data in order to provide a higher weight to the samples with larger losses, since it is more important that the classifier is correct for these training samples.

9 Team Members

Jonathan Sadeghi: Jonathan is a final year PhD student at the Institute for Risk and Uncertainty (University of Liverpool). He is interested in applying probabilistic techniques to engineering problems where there is poor quality data or a lack of appropriate data. In particular this involves machine learning techniques and generalisations of probability theory. He is grateful to have been the project facilitator for this accomplished, multidisciplinary team.

David Berman: David is a Professor of Theoretical Physics at Queen Mary University of London. His main research interests are in novel mathematical formulations of string and M-theory.

Shaoxiong Hu: Shaoxiong is a 3rd year PhD student of Statistics at Queen Mary, University of London. His PhD project is to apply the topological and algebraic criterion in statistical model selection.

Nam Pho: Nam is a graduate student in computer science at the Georgia Institute of Technology and research associate at Harvard Medical School studying the contribution of environmental factors towards disease.

Marc Williams: Marc is computational biology PhD student at UCL. His main interest is in applying theoretical models to understanding biological systems.

Diego Arenas: Diego is an EngD in Computer Science student at the University of St Andrews.

Alvaro Cabrejas Egea: Alvaro is a PhD student at the Center for Complexity Science (University of Warwick). He focuses on traffic modelling, forecasting and control using time series and reinforcement learning.

Fangfang Niu: Fangfang is a data science graduate with a special focus on NLP. She has a PhD in Theoretical Linguistics from Queen Mary University of London. She has worked on sentiment analysis, text modeling and text classification.

Medb Corcoran: Medb is Director of Applied Intelligence at the Dock, Accenture's Global Innovation Center in Dublin, Ireland.

Simon Frost: Simon is a Reader in Pathogen Dynamics at the University of Cambridge, and a Turing Fellow, working on real-time analytics for infectious disease surveillance. Simon contributed to the time series analysis and simulation of event counts.

Lukas Danev: Lukas is a recent graduate of Master of Informatics from Edinburgh University with focus on data science and natural language processing. He has worked on the event classification based on free text description with LSTM neural network.

Kumutha Swampillai: A Data Science Consultant at Accenture with a research background in language modelling for speech recognition and a PhD in NLP from Sheffield University.

References

- [1] *Machine learning helps banks cut fraud and prep stress tests*. Financial Times, 2018.
- [2] Tsay, R.S. *Analysis of financial time series*. John Wiley & Sons, 2005.
- [3] R.B. Cleveland et al. *STL: A Seasonal-Trend Decomposition Procedure based on LOESS*. Journal of Official Statistics, 6 (1): 3-73, 1990.
- [4] Radim Řehůřek and Petr Sojka *Software Framework for Topic Modelling with Large Corpora*. Proceedings of the LREC 2010 Workshop on New Challenges for NLP Frameworks, 45-50, 2010
- [5] Pritchard, J. K.; Stephens, M.; Donnelly, P. *Inference of population structure using multilocus genotype data*. Genetics. 155 (2): 945-959, 2000.
- [6] Kemp, C D; Kemp, A W. *Some properties of the Hermite distribution*. Biometrika, 52 (3-4): 381-394, 1965. doi: 10.1093/biomet/52.3-4.381

turing.ac.uk
@turinginst